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IMPACT OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY ON THE LABOR MARKET IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The article examines the impact of circular economy (CE) principles on the labor market in developing countries. It analyzes job creation opportunities in the recycling and restoration sectors, as well as the implications for traditional industries such as mining and agriculture. The study explores how the shift to CE drives economic and social changes, including workforce redistribution and the need for workforce retraining. It also evaluates the influence of CE on reducing environmental risks and improving resource efficiency. The article discusses the mechanisms of government support and investments needed for the successful implementation of circular models and for boosting employment across various economic sectors.

Keywords: *circular economy (CE), labor market (LM), developing countries, sustainable development, green technologies, workforce retraining.*

Introduction

The circular economy (CE) is an economic model focused on minimizing waste and maximizing the efficient use of resources through reuse, recycling, and recovery. In the context of global environmental crisis risks and the limited availability of natural resources, CE is emerging as a key aspect of sustainable development (SD) capable of transforming traditional economic practices and approaches to production and consumption.

In recent decades, many developed countries have actively implemented CE principles, aiming to reduce their environmental impact and decrease dependency on imported raw materials. However, in developing countries, the transition to CE faces several challenges, including limited financial resources, insufficient technological infrastructure, and a high reliance on traditional economic activities. Nevertheless, the adoption of CE in these countries can become not only a tool of environmental policy but also a source of significant socio-economic changes.

The labor market (LM) in developing countries is characterized by high employment levels in sectors such as agriculture and extractive industries. At the same time, it is in these sectors that the problems of environmental protection are most clearly manifested, which creates the need to move to more sustainable business models. The introduction of the CE can lead to both the creation of new jobs and the loss of existing

ones, which makes the analysis of this process especially important.

The aim of this article is to examine the impact of implementing CE principles on the LM in developing countries. The article addresses the issues of job creation and redistribution in specific sectors, as well as the socio-economic consequences of LM changes and the need for workforce retraining.

Main part. Principles of the CE

The approach aimed at resource conservation and minimizing environmental impact through the reduction, recycling, and reuse of materials is known as the CE. According to the Circularity Gap Report 2024, despite the growing popularity of CE principles and the increase in initiatives in this field, global circularity continues to decline – the share of secondary materials decreased from 9,1% in 2018 to 7,2% in 2023 [1]. This highlights the need for radical measures and systemic changes to reduce resource overconsumption, which is largely driven by traditional linear economic models.

It is known that countries are classified by their levels of economic development into developed, developing and least developed (underdeveloped). Developed countries are characterized by a high level of GDP, industrialization and high quality of life, while developing countries have a lower level of income and underdeveloped infrastructure. The least developed countries face poverty, lack of industry and a weak economic base. Different groups of countries have different impacts on the environment (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Environmental impact of different country groups, % [1]

To mitigate the negative impact on the environment and ensure SD, it is necessary to implement the principles of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) aimed at optimizing the use of resources and

minimizing waste. They include extending the life cycle of products, using renewable and secondary materials, as well as implementing recycling technologies and restoring products (table 1).

Table 1.

Main principles of the CE and their descriptions [2, 3]

Principles of CE	Description	Examples
Sustainable resource management	Optimization of resource use, waste reduction, and minimizing environmental impact.	Implementation of eco-habits like wisely use of energy sources and water.
Extension of product life cycle	Increasing the lifespan of products through their repair, restore, and modernization into something new.	Repairing programs, exchange of old products and things for upgrades or reuse.
Implementation of recycling and recovery technologies	Application of innovative methods for recycling materials and extracting valuable resources from waste.	Plastic recycling, materials production from recycled resources.
Service-based business models	Provision of services instead of product sales, which improves usage efficiency and reduces resource consumption.	Car-sharing and rental of household appliances instead of purchasing.

As per the UNECE 2024 report, CE has the potential to decrease global environmental impacts and efficiently utilize natural resources. Implementing circular strategies is expected to decrease worldwide greenhouse gas emissions by 39% by 2030 in comparison to levels in 2020, resulting in a yearly reduction of 22,8 billion tons of CO2 equivalent. It is also feasible to decrease the consumption of primary resources by 28%, leading to a saving of approximately 7,5 billion tons of raw materials every year.

Successful implementation of circular initiatives, such as recycling and reuse programs in countries like Kazakhstan, Georgia, and Belarus in the UNECE region, have led to a 60% reduction in materials sent to landfills and an increase in secondary processing to 50% by 2023 [4].

The accomplishments are made possible by digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI), which help improve resource management and reduce waste. Utilizing digital technology helps to enhance efficiency, leading to improved management of supply chains and more precise tracking of resource usage. The impact is especially evident in emerging nations like Uzbekistan, where the

adoption of digital technologies has raised the proportion of recycled materials by 35% and is projected to further increase by 2030, supporting sustainable economic development and lessening environmental effects [5].

The CE is essential in revolutionizing economic frameworks by providing sustainable options to traditional methods and facilitating a shift in the nature of employment. This transformation requires the adaptation of national economic strategies and the development of educational programs to prepare specialists capable of supporting the transition to sustainable production and consumption models.

Impact of the CE on unemployment rates and workforce redistribution

According to UNCTAD projections, the **global transition to a CE** could create over 7 million jobs and generate economic growth of up to 4,5 trillion dollars by 2030 [6]. Promising sectors for job creation include plastic waste recycling, bioproduct manufacturing, and the repair and restoration of industrial products.

An example of successful implementation of circular principles is the «Zero Waste in the Caribbean» project, carried out by UNEP. In 2023, this initiative

created over 200,000 jobs in **Caribbean countries** (Dominican Republic, Grenada, and Jamaica) through the development of waste management systems aligned with CE principles [7].

According to **Georgia's** roadmap for transitioning to a CE by 2050, the plan aims to significantly increase material recycling rates and reduce waste, creating new jobs in environmentally friendly sectors. Research done by the Georgian Society of Nature Explorers «Orchis» (GSNE Orchis) pinpointed major sectors with strong circular potential and aimed to raise waste-free production from 1,3% in 2023 to 9,1% in the next 5-10 years [8].

For example, **Russia** is considered an emerging economy, however, it stands out from other developing nations due to its abundant natural resources and a substantial industrial sector. In the year 2024, the effect of the CE on the job market was evident in a rise in employment, particularly in the processing and manufacturing industries. Research conducted by the National Research University Higher School of Economics showed a rise of 261,800 employees in the manufacturing industry compared to the previous year. Other sectors also saw growth, such as in the transport and trade sectors, where employment increased by 46,3 thousand and 22 thousand people, respectively [9].

In the long term, the transition to a CE is expected to lead to a redistribution of the workforce, as traditional industries such as mining and primary materials production begin to lose their relevance and reduce their production volumes [10]. This is because the CE aims to minimize the use of non-renewable resources and encourage the reuse of materials, which reduces the demand for primary extraction and production. Thus, sectors of the economy that have long been the main sources of employment will gradually give way to new, more environmentally sustainable industries. In emerg-

ing economies, where a significant part of the workforce is employed in such traditional sectors, this will cause structural changes.

Changes in skill requirements and the need for workforce retraining

As the CE demands the implementation of new technologies, workers must acquire skills that were not previously needed in traditional sectors such as mining and primary production.

For example, in **Indonesia and Vietnam**, UNDP is implementing projects aimed at training workers in waste recycling and bioproduct manufacturing skills. Special attention is given to vulnerable groups who were previously employed in traditional agricultural sectors. The programs include training in new methods of recycling plastics and organic waste and producing low-carbon products.

In **Egypt**, a workforce retraining program supported by the World Bank and the Ministry of Environment of Egypt (MOE) focuses on skill development in CE sectors such as waste management and recycling. The program involves the creation of training centers and the organization of workshops where participants learn about circular production methods and waste recycling, particularly in construction materials and organic waste. These initiatives align with Egypt's long-term goal of enhancing resilience and creating new jobs under the Egypt Vision 2030 strategy.

The UNIDO report emphasizes that the introduction of closed production cycles involves the transition of workers to new sectors and contributes to the increase of added value in the economy. An assessment of the socio-economic effects of the introduction of the CE based on the NICE (National Impacts of CE) model showed that retraining programs can significantly increase the level of employment among vulnerable groups (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Socio-economic impact of CE projects (increase of employment level), thousands of people [11]

The data were collected through surveys conducted under UNIDO-initiated projects in countries such as Egypt, Indonesia and Vietnam. The socio-economic impact was assessed using the Eora multi-regional input-output model, which takes into account inter-regional interactions and changes in supply chains.

The results were calculated based on detailed data on the activities of participating enterprises, including their costs and savings achieved through the introduction of innovative technologies and sustainable production processes.

In **Africa**, the Africa Circular Economy Facility (CEF) program, supported by the African Development Bank, has launched retraining initiatives in five countries, including Zambia and Nigeria. These programs are aimed at training workers in waste management, developing skills in the field of digitalization and using innovative approaches in agriculture. Such measures can significantly reduce the dependence of these countries on imported resources and increase employment in the processing and renewable energy sectors.

In **Latin American** countries, for example, Colombia and Peru, thanks to the support of the World Bank and the International Labour Organization (ILO), training and skills development programs in the field of renewable energy and sustainable agriculture have been launched. In particular, the training centers offer courses on the installation and maintenance of solar and

wind installations, as well as on the introduction of environmentally friendly agricultural technologies.

In **Russia**, the national projects «Ecology» and «Clean Country» contribute to the development of CE. These programs are designed to decrease waste and enhance resource utilization. As part of these projects, staff members are undergoing training, which includes developing skills in handling recycled materials and adopting eco-friendly technologies. This helps not just in being eco-friendly, but also in generating new jobs aligned with the contemporary needs of the CE, bolstering the nation's economy and decreasing its ecological impact.

Typically, employees need various professional qualities and skills to comply with CE requirements, ensuring successful implementation and management of sustainable practices (table 2).

Table 2.

Professional competencies of employees in the transition to the CE

Competency category	Description	Relevance for CE
Technical skills	Knowledge of recycling and waste management technologies; working with sustainable materials.	Ensuring technological efficiency and sustainability.
Environmental literacy	Understanding CE principles and the environmental impact of production processes.	Minimizing the negative environmental impact.
Digital literacy	Ability to work with digital tools for resource management and data analysis.	Process optimization and resource management.
Analytical thinking	Ability to analyze and optimize processes; finding solutions to enhance sustainability and efficiency.	Seeking innovative solutions and improving efficiency.

The CE has a multifaceted impact on the LM, bringing both positive and negative consequences. On one hand, it creates new jobs in sectors such as recycling, resource management, and eco-friendly production, which contributes to economic growth and reduces unemployment levels. On the other hand, it necessitates significant changes in traditional industries, such as mining and primary material production, which may lead to job losses. As the shift to new production models progresses, the need for workforce retraining and the development of new skills increases, allowing employees to adapt to changing demands and avoid the risk of unemployment.

Conclusion

The implementation of CE principles in developing countries has significant potential to transform the LM and create jobs in sectors such as waste recycling, resource management, and sustainable production. However, these changes require the redistribution of the workforce from traditional industries, such as agriculture and mining, which may lead to structural changes and social challenges. To transition to a CE, countries need to develop effective supportive measures to maximize socio-economic benefits while minimizing potential negative impacts on the LM and social stability.

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